

DOI:**ABSTRACT**

The use of latest trends and technologies in academic research may now be changing with such a frequency in the universities in terms of faculties who teaches and students that learn. Each and every universities wants to not only improve the syllabus but they also want to upgrade their labs with latest use of hardware and software. They are also focusing upon the technological growth of the students and their students can also develop their applications in different zones like traffic management for government, application that help to improve the lifestyle of the peoples. For academic institutions, stimulating with endowing graduates to contend in today's knowledge economy, the possibilities and promises are great. The universities is not only focusing to provide the education only to the students but they also taking in account of the research oriented work and freelancing to the students. But significant challenges also come into view. For all of its benefits, technology remains a upsetting innovation—and an exclusive one. Faculty members used to teaching in one way may be reluctant to invest the time to learn new methods, and may lack the budget for needed support.

KEYWORD: Clustered Storage, REST architecture, Automation, Storage resources.

INTRODUCTION

Digital education is one of the easiest education system that can be accessed from anywhere from different countries. But, in today's world, if we consider India than the peoples are not aware to access the resources digitally. To educate them and aware of the program makes the education learning system more effective and efficient. We need to educate the peoples so that they can able to use iPod, iphone and tabs, computers so that they can educate themselves as well as their children's.

As we have already know that the maximum percentage from different sectors has agree upon the fact that technology has changed the teaching methodology and nearly about more than 60% people will say that. This will be huge in the next coming years. As we know that the television is one of the digital way where parents can teach their students. The poems, the mathematical calculation can be easily available and now taking the advantage is not only saving the time but also making their efficiency.

Students will also taking the part in distance learning and online learning programs. In the universities and colleges also the digital learning has the significant meaning. The colleges also opening some center where video conferences, workshop lectures can be organized not only for the students but also for the faculties. Faculty development programmes in the colleges are taking on the regular basis so that the faculties will aware of new trends and technologies and their guidance is beneficial for the students.

Every college is now maintaining the alumni with the use of latest technology & trends so that their regular updates in the industry will benefit to their juniors. Institute industry interaction is also becoming the part of teaching and regularly the experts from the industries are taking the part for the betterment of students.

HOW TECHNOLOGY IS CHANGING TODAY'S CLASSROOMS

Technology is enabling multi-modal teaching, changing curricula and spawning rich forms of online research and collaboration. Nearly 60% of survey respondents say that professors will soon teach in more than one medium. At some places classroom courses are filled with three cameras and a sound mixer. The course goes online within 30 minutes, says Mr Delaney. "Within 24 hours, students interested in reviewing a certain case or topic can click an online index that charts the content of the entire class and can view the portion that interests them."

When asked to compare different communications technologies, 52% of survey respondents state that online collaboration tools would make the greatest contribution in terms of improving educational quality over the next five years—the top response—while 48% point to the dynamic delivery of content and software that supports individually paced learning. Sophisticated learning-management systems and enhanced video and presentation tools are among other innovations that respondents say are likely to have a profound effect on the academic experience.

It's a view that others across the higher-education spectrum share. "The professor's role is evolving from instructor to mentor. Homework, quizzes and projects will have to be designed in such a way as to require genuine thoughtfulness on the part of the student. That paradigm shift offers enormous potential for advancing educational quality."

Finally, respondents foresee an interesting range of possibilities regarding how technology is most likely to affect future academic offerings, spurred by innovative faculty research, student engagement and the pursuit of academic collaboration. Over the next five years, 56% of respondents expect to see a greater number of interdisciplinary majors, combining chemical engineering and environmental studies for instance, and 43% foresee broader inter-university collaboration among students from multiple institutions. Looking beyond the five-year horizon, more than two-thirds of all respondents say that students will be able to craft individualized degree programmes, either within their own university or by bundling coursework from different institutions. And more than one-half see the publishing world evolving as a result of all these developments, with textbooks and printed documents eventually being replaced by online materials. "The rise of online peer review may mean that some texts exist exclusively in virtual form, where they can be updated.

LITERATURE SURVEY

How is technology most likely to affect academic course and degree offerings in your country?

(% respondents)

■ Within five years ■ Longer than five years ■ Unlikely to occur ■ Don't know

Courses will vary in length, rather than being semester-based

Dynamic delivery of content will allow coursework to adjust to a student's performance level

Traditional credit requirements will change

A greater number of interdisciplinary majors will be offered

More inter-university collaboration on individual coursework will be available (ie, students from different institutions may work together on a given topic)

Students will be able to mix and match classes from various institutions to meet degree requirements

Students will be able to customize their own degrees

A rise in partnerships between universities and corporations will lead more professionals to pursue highly specialized certification programmes

52 30 8 9
A rise in partnerships between universities and corporations will lead more students to seek specialized degrees

54 28 8 10

Which tools does your institution currently use, and which do you think will be used within five years?

(% respondents)

Use Within Don't know/Not
now five years applicable

With regard to the following, how well prepared do you feel your country's university and college students are to compete in today's global marketplace?

Please rate on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1=Well prepared and 5=Not at all prepared.

(% respondents)

1 Well prepared 2 3 4 5 Not at all prepared Don't know

Environmental and social issues

Overall job readiness

CHALLENGES IN REWIRING EDUCATION

Previously from the statistical data we have seen that more than one-third of those polled believe that tenure and promotional requirements will need to be re-weighted to include technology-based teaching criteria.

Although university participants view technology as having a largely positive impact on their campuses, they acknowledge several challenges. The biggest of these may well be cost, a factor that close to 70% of university respondents cite as their greatest concern. Entrenched organizational cultures may be another hurdle, as academic faculty members accustomed to traditional modes of instruction may be disinclined to change. They may find themselves difficult to adjust with new teaching methodology and may even feel that uncomfortableness with the newer means to teach the younger generation and may not be able to cope up with the expectations of the younger one's. then there is the question of IT's alignment with overall leadership and policy setting.

Inside the classroom, technology may be a disruptive innovation in ways not intended. Survey participants along with those interviewed note that pervasive multi-tasking between laptop, smart-phone and other technologies in the classroom often distracts students. no matter how serious lecture or discussion is going on, the availability of gadgets and their multi-functionality to the students may distract them to other leisure spending things that are there in the devices. This can be true even in highly disciplined institutions and many other universities present all over the world. People in technical field information technology field education field have discussing upon this topic and they say that "it is impossible to sit someone in front of the world wide web and expect them not to use it. There are n number of things and options that strike and pop-up like bubbles out of boiling water as we find ourselves in front of it .it is a giant source to explore everything from entertainment to leisure and from politics to movies and other interesting things in the world. We, as faculty, teachers and administrators have to recognize that if we're going to use technology in the classroom, we must find additional ways to keep content meaningful, even if it comes down to the simple task of requesting computer monitors down during the instructional period and back up during the hands-on portion of class." we must have some tracking algorithm's to keep a check on students that they are not indulged into something which affects their studies by using this teaching methodology. That is, they use the internet for some fruitful purposes and listen carefully to what is being taught to them. We must limit their content access in a positive manner so that they are neither bored, deprived of utilities nor they misuse the resources.

Respondents also associate the increased use of new technologies in the classroom with a rise in plagiarism and cheating. At the University of Illinois, Dr Johnson was surprised to see instances of discourteous behavior among students operating in the online environment. "Perhaps due to the relative anonymity of that forum, students appear to take more liberties online than they would in class." Many respondents (56%) cite easy access to online reference material as one of the greatest risks posed by the continued adoption of new technologies. Lieutenant Colonel Conti and his colleague, Lieutenant Colonel Ed Sobiesk, who run the university's Core Information Technology Program. To this problem, many solutions were discussed like as we discussed above proper use of tracking algorithm and limitation of content access over the web and into the device through the internet.

CONCLUSION

These changes will have a significant ripple effect on higher education. Over the next decade, advanced technologies will put education within the reach of many more individuals around the world, and will allow greater specialization in curriculum and teaching methodologies than ever before. With these benefits comes the challenge of ensuring that university infrastructure and operations are in place to support the adoption of technology on campus. As ever, administrators will need to weigh carefully how budget funds are spent, decide what emerging

technologies show the most promise, and determine how best to support these technological advances while avoiding the ever-present risk of obsolescence.

But perhaps the most critical question facing the academic world is something far more fundamental: namely, what it will mean to be an educated person in the 21st century. As our study indicates, these sweeping technological changes will effectively change the skill-sets of the future workforce, as well as its approach to work in general. As a result, societies around the world will need to consider how to make the most of these new opportunities and thus ensure that they remain competitive in the global marketplace.

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